

Article Evaluation

Coupled neural systems underlie the production and comprehension of naturalistic narrative speech

by Lauren J. Silbert, Christopher J. Honey, Erez Simony, David Poeppel, and Uri Hasson (2014)

Introduction

The article shows that there are extensively overlapping brain responses between a speaker and a listener, as well as within and across speakers, in a face-to-face conversation using functional MRI and a time-warping method. This study addresses the challenge of mapping the spatial overlap between speech production and perception systems through the retelling method. In this article evaluation, four main aspects — content, methodology, language, and format — will be discussed, along with the evaluation against the provided background material (Uri Hasson's videos on brain-to-brain coupling) and other materials present in the course. Other observations and conclusions will be mentioned towards the end.

Aspect 1: Content

1.1. Strengths

- The motivation of this article is novel. It reveals how the brain processes language in a two-way speech setting examining the brain scans of both speaker and listener engaging in the same communicative session.
- A caveat of this study that a speaker may listen to him or herself while speaking in the Discussion section is well thought and statistically argued.

1.2. Misarrangements

- While the paper discusses extralinguistic features, it could improve clarity on what these entail from the beginning. The first mention of extralinguistic features is that they are related to social aspects of the told story¹. Then, they are mentioned again with relevance to the interlocutors in the Discussion section². After reading the first mention, a reader might assume that they are not of the interlocutors, or a reader might form a question if they are supposed to be related to the interlocutors as well. It should be made clear from the beginning what extralinguistic features entail or at least specify that more aspects will be found to be involved in a later stage.
- The paper mentions a gap in previous studies regarding the recruitment of extralinguistic areas during real-life speech production³; however, it could specify this earlier in the introduction before the aim of the study⁴.

¹ "Significant reliability was also observed in a collection of extralinguistic areas implicated in the processing of semantic and social aspects of the story..."

² "...social functions that should indeed be shared across interlocutors, such as the ability to infer the mental states of others..."

³ "It is not known whether production of real-life speech will also recruit these extralinguistic areas."

⁴ "This study pursues three aims:..."

- Comparative analysis with other studies in the beginning of the Discussion section could be better placed in the introduction for better contextualization^{5 6}. Alternatively, what should be potentially discussed in the Discussion can be about how the results of this study relate to other studies.

1.3. More Explanations Needed

- The paper could better explain how inconsistencies in repetitive speech production affect the mapping of audio with brain scans.
- It is common to make an assumption of certain phenomena encountered during the experiments in the Discussion section, but the assumption needs to be backed up with research⁷.
- Clarity is needed regarding the challenges of studying brain activity during speech production and comprehension, including why this is not commonly conducted⁸. Based on the paper, the spatiotemporal complexity of natural language can be further explained by specifying “the inconsistency of the repetitive speech produced by a speaker in terms of duration and acoustic features.”

Aspect 2: Methodology

- The paper employs various methodologies to enhance the reliability of the results that, at the same time, could be restrictions.
 - The researchers handle the limitation of recording speech production systems by making participants tell a story repeatedly and make sure that the retellings are spoken in the same manner.
 - The study employs the intra-subject correlation analysis including time-warping method to minimize the variations between retellings. The comparison between time-warping, which is more adaptive in aligning audio envelopes, and linear interpolation method is also explained in detail.
 - While these methodologies add up the rigidity of the study, they also create limitations which narrow the generalization of the results under the conducted conditions.

2.1. Missing Details

- The paper acknowledges potential adaption effects from participants rehearsing narratives; however, it should include the related experiment or references⁹.

⁵ “A major difference between this study and all others investigating language processing is the production task.”

⁶ “In addition, analytical methods differ greatly between this study and previous ones...”

⁷ “During comprehension, these areas may receive input from early auditory areas and serve as an entry point for the analysis of the speech sounds properties, whereas during production these areas might be needed to monitor the precision of the speech output.”

⁸ “owing to both the spatiotemporal complexity of natural language and an insufficient understanding of language-related neural processes, it is challenging to use conventional hypothesis-driven functional MRI (fMRI) analysis methods for modeling the brain activity acquired during long segments of natural speech. These challenges have mired our ability to fully characterize the production system.”

⁹ “Adaptation is the reduction in neural activity when stimuli are repeated. It has been reported robustly and at multiple spatial scales from individual cortical neurons to hemodynamic changes using fMRI.”

- The paper could better address whether the experimental setup truly represents natural communication. Although the first round of retellings is spontaneous, this repetition does not occur in real-life situations.
- The paper should include more details about the questionnaire to test the understanding of perceived speech. The 115-point true/false questionnaire has a 50/50 chance of being correct, the author should specify how the questionnaire is designed to handle this limitation; for example, repeating the same questions in a different wording in a random position throughout the questionnaire. Tang et al. (2023) dedicated a section explaining how the questionnaire, which is called “Behavioral Comprehension Assessment”, is used.

2.2. Others

- The study recruits a small number of participants, which makes it challenging to generalize the results.
- The experiment in the section “Reproduction of Real-Life Story by Secondary Speakers.” is not exactly a replication of the main experiment because in the main experiment, the participants speak directly from their experience while in this experiment, the secondary speakers speak from the memorization of the primary story. This experiment is more to test if the same brain activity can be reproduced when a speaker tells a memorized story compared to a direct experience.

Aspect 3: language

3.1. Strengths

- The use of the main idea sentence in the beginning of each paragraph largely helps readers in understanding the technical text, especially when discussing limitations in the Introduction part^{10 11 12 13}.
- A variety of connecting and transitional words are used appropriately and effectively throughout the paper: in addition (4 times), moreover (8 times), therefore (3 times), however (11 times), nonetheless (1 time), and finally (6 times).

3.2. Ambiguous or Too Technical Language Use

- The paper could provide more specific descriptions of “complex real-life speech” mentioned in the first paragraph related to assessing brain activity¹⁴.
- The assessment of brain activity during speech production and comprehension (the third aim in the Introduction section) could be clarified in which aspects of the assessment will be discussed¹⁵.

¹⁰ “The functional-anatomic architecture underlying the production of speech in an ecological context is incompletely characterized.”

¹¹ “Mapping the cortical attributes of the production system during natural speech is further complicated by methodological challenges related to the motor variability across repeated speech acts (retellings)”

¹² “Uncertainty about the extent of the production system hindered attempts at mapping the full spatial overlap between the production and comprehension systems”

¹³ “Finally, mapping the extent of spatial overlap between comprehension and production of real-life speech is necessary but not sufficient for understanding the relationship between the two processes.”

¹⁴ “In this study we used a new approach to functional MRI acquisition and analysis to characterize the neural responses during production and comprehension of complex real-life speech.”

¹⁵ “to assess the coupling between activity in the speaker’s brain during naturalistic production and activity in the listener’s brain during comprehension of the same narrative.”

- The following sentence should be made clear about whose production system is not recorded (speaker or listener or both?)¹⁶. Based on the mention of the previous publication where the brain activities of a listener is predicted using the brain responses of a speaker, it can be assumed that in this sentence, the production system of both speaker and listener is not recorded.
- Technical language could be explained using more accessible terms; for example, the part that differentiates linear interpolation method and time-warp analysis.
- The name of the section “Time-Warp Analysis” sounds more like a method or a procedure than an analysis.
- The term “speech acts” is used confusingly in the paper without a clear explanation although in the first use it is accompanied by (retellings). Speech acts are commonly referred linguistically to actions performed through speech that also serves social purposes like assertives, directives, commissives, expressives, and declaratives. In this article, this term is used more generally as the act of speaking, which can cause confusion.

3.3. Suggestion for a Stronger Effect

- In the following sentence where the argument of distinctiveness of the results is introduced, the emphasis should be more on the experimental design of real-time communication, which is a more special aspect of this study, instead of the left-brain lateralization dominance of linguistic tasks¹⁷.

Aspect 4: Format

- Titles and subtitles are used effectively helping to enhance readability.
- In-text references and supporting information could be better integrated, and more figures could be included within the main text. In-text references should be made distinctive from a normal text by either using the common format with author’s name and year or using different fonts¹⁸. In addition, supporting visualizations should be in the same file as the main article. For example, Figure S4 and Table S1 require opening an external link to read. The article currently has only 5 figures and can definitely include more relevant visual information given the complexity of the topics.

5. Evaluation against background material and other studies introduced in the course

5.1. Background material (Uri Hasson’s videos on brain-to-brain coupling)

- Uri Hasson’s talk (2019) emphasizes on the transfer of information from a speaker to a listener as a speaker intends to evoke similar brain activities in a listener’s brain. This is seen as a collective phenomenon as illustrated in the visualization from one speaker to possibly many listeners [minute 6:43]. The video describes how a speaker who tells a story from a memory or the past can replicate their perspective on a listener’s brain, and a listener also predicts the story beforehand. The study he mentioned in his talk relied on a

¹⁶ “Recently, we reported neural coupling across a speaker and a group of listeners during natural communication (33). However, that study did not map the production system.”

¹⁷ “The results indicate that production of a real-life narrative is not localized to the left hemisphere but recruits an extensive bilateral network, which overlaps extensively with the comprehension system.”

¹⁸ “the production of single phonemes (1–5), words (6–8), or short phrases in decontextualized, isolated environments (9–13)”.

recorded and play-back audio; however, in this article (2014), although not explicitly mentioning whether the experimental setup involves face-to-face conversation or audio playback, it can be assumed to be face-to-face conversation provided extralinguistic features are mentioned.

- The study in Uri Hasson's talk manipulates the audio in a more variety of ways – by playing soundbites in reverse, scrambling words, sentences, or paragraphs – while this article only provides random strings of sounds referred to as a “nonsense phrase”¹⁹. Both methods serve different purposes: the first one disturbs the temporal order or coherency of the story while the second one filters out audio-region brain responses.
- The study of Lerner and team (2011) mentioned in Uri's talk involves a more complex experimental setting than the one in this article and reveals that different listeners share the same brain responses when listening to the same story. In addition, the results of Stephens and team's study (2010) mentioned in the talk are also analyzed in a more fine-grained manner, discovering the different levels of comprehension among listeners based on the brain scan.

5.2. Comparison with other studies in the course

- The proposed coupling model is innovative and unprecedented. It also adds up on top of the previous study²⁰. The paper could, however, provide more explanation of the potential applications and utility of the coupling model.
- The result that different stories have different brain responses is in line with the study of Tang et al. (2023). This is mentioned in the “Brain Areas Are Aligned Across Speech Acts Only When Speakers Produce the Exact Same Speech Utterance” section. Tang and a team, relying on fMRI and a semantic language decoder based on a contextual language model (GPT), found that the neural activities differ when a speaker tells different stories. However, the following sentence in this section can confuse readers that no differences of the brain scan between the two stories are identified²¹. The phrase “reliable responses” should be replaced with a more literal term.
- The result of brain scan in this study that a listener and a speaker shares is only those with higher-level of process (meaning and concept) not low-level audio features differs from other studies where audio brain regions are also involved in speech perception²². The article “Speech rhythms and their neural foundations” by David Poeppel and M. Florencia Assaneo (2020) introduces a model suggesting that the system in our brain responsible for producing speech acts like a rhythm generator, and it syncs up with the part of our brain responsible for understanding speech. In addition, Hickok and Poeppel (2007) found a shared active brain region during speech production and perception²³.

6. Other Observations and Conclusions

¹⁹ “goo da ga ba la la la fee foo fa”

²⁰ “To measure the coupling between production and comprehension mechanisms, we formulated, in a previous publication, a model of the expected responses in the listener's brain during speech comprehension based on the speaker's responses during speech production.”

²¹ “We find no significant reliable responses between these two different speech productions.”

²² “As a result, we are confident that the widespread areas that responded reliably during speech comprehension and production are tied to the processing of linguistic and extralinguistic content and not to the processing of low-level audio features.”

²³ “The STS [the middle to posterior portions of the superior temporal sulcus] is activated by language tasks that require access to phonological information, including both the perception and production of speech.”

- The fact that the brain activity in the areas related to semantic and grammatical content are active in repeated speech of the same story is surprising²⁴. Similar to mantra, this type of repeated utterance barely requires any effort in a way that the brain has to pull up from a memory or interpret anything. It makes sense that the motor areas are recruited, but it is counter-intuitive that the areas related to comprehension and grammatical structure are also still activated after many repetitions. This might be due to the frequencies and duration of the repetitions. The more a speech is uttered, the less effort is required. The repetitions in this study may not occur often enough and over a long enough period of time for the brain to get used to to the point that it no longer processes the meaning. This might also be the explanation why the brain activity patterns of spontaneous and rehearsed speech in this study are similar but just weaker over time.
- Because of these tiny gaps of time between each retelling, I wonder if it would be valid to claim that the occurrence of similar brain responses across the retellings is evidence that those brain activities are related to language only, not other factors like extralinguistic features, because the circumstances of the experiment do not change either. This is mentioned in the last paragraph of the Introduction before Results²⁵.
- Hopefully in the future, there will be imaging tools that can capture brain activities during real-time communication effectively enough to accommodate this type of research questions without restrictive experimental conditions.

References:

Hasson, Uri. 2019. *Time Regained: Using Storytelling to Share Memories Across Brains*. <https://www.ibiology.org/neuroscience/storytelling-and-memories/>. (March 2, 2024).

Hickok, Gregory & Poeppel David. 2007. The cortical organization of speech processing. *Nat Rev Neurosci* 8(5). 393-402. 10.1038/nrn2113.

Lerner, Yulia, Honey, Christopher J., Silbert, Lauren J. & Hasson, Uri. 2011. Topographic Mapping of a Hierarchy of Temporal Receptive Windows Using a Narrated Story. *Journal of Neuroscience* 31(8). 2906-15. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.3684-10.2011>.

Poeppel, David & Assaneo, Florencia M. 2020. Speech rhythms and their neural foundations. *Nat Rev Neurosci* 21(6). 322-34. 10.1038/s41583-020-0304-4.

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²⁴ "These areas responded in a reliable manner within the speaker's brain across multiple productions of the same 15-min story."

²⁵ "An area involved in both speech production and speech comprehension can nonetheless perform different functions across the two tasks. In contrast, if similar functions are being recruited during the production and comprehension of speech, then the brain responses over time will be correlated (coupled) across the speaker's and the listener's brains."

Stephens, Greg J., Silbert, Lauren J. & Hasson, Uri. 2010. Speaker–listener neural coupling underlies successful communication. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 107(32). 14425-30. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1008662107>.

Tang, Jerry, LeBel, Amanda, Jain, Shailee & Huth, Alexander. 2023. Semantic reconstruction of continuous language from non-invasive brain recordings. *Nat Neurosci* 26. 858–66. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41593-023-01304-9>.